

PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO NON-PHILOLOGY B2 LEVEL STUDENTS BASED ON THE STATE EDUCATION STANDARDS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the teaching of English to non-philological students and the level of ESP students in the state education standards according to the CEFR international assessment system. Although ESP education has taken an important place in the curriculum of non-philology majors of all higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, the expected result of learning English at the specified level has not been achieved in most students. Therefore, at first, we preferred to get acquainted with the requirements for each skill of the language in the state educational standard for non-philology students. It is known that in ESP education, unlike ELT, the course is designed based on the learner's goals and needs. During the course, the student partially learns the rules of the general English language, and mainly the expression of words and terms related to his professional field in English.*

Keywords: *ESP, ELT, National State Standards, CEFR, non-philology*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini nofilologik yo'nalish talabalariga o'qitish va davlat ta'lim standartlarida ESP talabalarining CEFR xalqaro baholash tizimiga muvofiq qaysi darajani egallashlari kerakligi to'g'risida bahs yuritadi. Garchi ESP ta'limi O'zbekistondagi barcha oliy ta'lim muassasalari nofilologik yo'nalishlari o'quv dasturidan muhim o'rin egallagan bo'lsada, hanz ko'pchilik talabalarda ingliz tilini belgilangan darajada o'rganish borasida kutilgan natijaga erishilgani yo'q. Shu sababli, dastlab, davlat ta'lim standartida aynan nofilologik yo'nalish talabalariga uchun tilning har bir ko'nikmasi bo'yicha qo'yilgan talablar bilan tanishib chiqishni ma'qul ko'rdik. Ma'lumki, ESP ta'limida ELT dan farqli ravishda o'rganuvchining maqsadi va ehtiyoji asosida kurs tashkil etiladi. Kurs davomida talaba qisman umumiy ingliz tili qoidalari, va asosan, kasbiy sohasiga aloqador so'z va terminlarning ingliz tilida ifodalanishini o'rganadi.*

Introduction

As a result of the great globalization, the borders between the countries were removed, the countries of the world sought to strengthen economic, political, trade and social relations, international solidarity and development. In these processes, the English language began to take an active part in the language and intercultural relations of modern society, as a language serving business affairs and information exchange. As a result of the high demand for the spread of the English language, there was a need to train native speakers and specialists who can communicate freely in this language, both locally and internationally, and to teach English. The idea of learning English for specific purposes, different approaches and studies have been developed since the 1970s. Initially, hundreds of studies were conducted on the prevalence and importance of the English for Specific Purposes (ESP) model in education outside of the United States and the United Kingdom, particularly in Central and South America, China, and Hong Kong. The main purpose of this was to develop the English language based on the interests and needs of university students or representatives of the field, words belonging to a certain area of the language or a specific language skill. Another important reason for applying the ESP approach in education is the formation of students' ability to communicate in international circles, to meet the requirements of

public exchange, to write and read in a foreign language. As a clear example of the importance of ESP, in the early years, special ESP and EAP courses were organized in universities of countries such as Great Britain, USA, Denmark, and Sweden. For more than 50 years, ESP education has been adopted in all countries of the world, and thousands of local studies have been conducted, and language courses have been organized in professional circles.

In Asian countries with different politics, economy and culture, English has become the language of education, business, travel, politics and diplomacy, the Internet, and has played an important role in the exchange of experience and knowledge in science and technology. As a result, many universities in Asia started offering English language courses for representatives of science, business communication and tourism in their educational programs. In particular, it can be recognized that the ESP training course established at the University of Singapore has been the main center for teaching professional English to 10,000 young students. Another work done on ESP is the establishment of the Asian ESP journal, which, apart from EAP, ESP, focuses on English for various strategic, economic, political, tourism and business purposes. , it was intended to cover issues related to the development of special English language programs for medical and service personnel, airline attendants, and hotel staff. Today, the magazine collects articles and theses promoting the development of resources for teaching English for specific purposes, testing methods and approaches, as well as harmonizing education with culture.

Although the implementation of the ESP approach in Uzbekistan has been slow, we can see its great development in recent years. In particular, in 2016, the EnSPIRe-U (English for specific purposes Integrated Reform in Uzbekistan) project, together with the Scientific and Practical Innovation Center under the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the British Embassy in Uzbekistan. developed a program, material and evaluation system for higher education institutions specializing in education. For the experiment, first 17 and later 14 universities from different places of the Republic were selected. At the end of the project, it was intended to develop special curricula and prepare materials to improve the level of knowledge of the English language in non-philological higher education institutions in the Republic, to form the lexicon of the English language related to the field. Based on the evidence collected as a result of the research, a holistic approach to the ESP teaching system was developed in the country. In the coming years, in 2018-2019, a number of modern methods, educational materials and lesson plans, coordinated with international standards (CEFR), were created on the basis of this project. The ESP model was developed in different countries in different ways and methods according to their geographical location, climate, industry and agriculture, specific conditions, social, cultural, political and economic views, and the lifestyle of their population. Also, factors such as mandatory and necessary conditions of industries and professions also affect the formation of ESP structure. The main goal expected from the project was to develop a work plan, resources, assessment system, training based on a national and unified approach to ESP education. Nukus State Pedagogical Institute was attached to the project on a pilot basis, where MA students from the Institute's English Language Department were trained in the ESP course and learned how to teach, assess, and use authentic language resources to meet ESP requirements. they got a nickname.

Review on previous literature

Currently, there are many monographs on ESP theory. Issues of the scientific-theoretical and methodological basis of the use of English language teaching technologies in the field of non-philological education in our country L.Kh. Alimzhanova, K. Zufarova, N.A. Mamatova, R.M.

Sobirova, Sh. Many monographs were created by scientists such as Rakhmatullaeva. Also, studies on the development of the English language aimed at the profession and various fields A.Kh. Juraev, Sh.P. Karimova, L.U.Kadirova, D.B.Kholboeva, D.J. Buranova, S.K. Yorova, Kh.D. Aymetova, N.Z. Ruziyeva, A.T. It was carried out by Mahkamboyev, H. A. Minavarov.

Scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States E. Kovachikova, F. Amariya, N. Prudnikova, S. V. Ryubishkinova, Tatiana V. Sidorenko, Eva Reid, B. Horvathova, Y. Y. Vyacheslavovna, L. B. Kuznetsova, I.Y. Schemelova, S.Yablokov, N.Astanina, N.Avsheniuk, S.Borg conducted scientific activities in the field of non-philological education, teaching English, developing the science program, evaluation system and technologies in ESP.

Internationally, hundreds of authors have conducted research on this topic: Strevens, P. (1988), Hutchinson, T. and Waters, A. (1987) were the first, and later Dudley-Evans, T. and St. . John, M. J. (1998). , Jones, A. M. and Price-Machado, D. (2001), Hyland, K. (2007), Catalin, I. (2014), Minodora, S. (2015), Lamry, C. E. (2016) and Bojovic, M. (2017). In the Cuban context: Castillo, M., Corona, D., Macola, C. and Peña, J. (1997), Diaz, G. (2000), Fonseca, A. B. (2002), Ramírez, I. (2004), Pupo , S. (2006), Castro, P., Gonzalez, G. and Casar, L. A. (2015) and Teruel, O. (2016) were developed.

Methods and methodology

The first program we studied is "Measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" on December 10, 2012 by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-1875, decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 8/2013 "Preparation of graduates of all stages of foreign language education" in May №124 based on requirements for the level of education and the Council of Europe "European competences for foreign language acquisition: learning, teaching and assessment" generally recognized international standards (CEFR - Common European Framework of Reference). The Cabinet of Ministers of Higher Education decided Bachelor's degree graduates of non-foreign language faculties must acquire the B2 level in the foreign language they have studied at the end of their four-year studies in the decree of "All stages of education in foreign languages".

Materials of the research

During the research, the ESP Curriculum published by the British Embassy in Uzbekistan in 2016-2022, decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, National State Standards were used.

Discussion

As a result of the conducted research, ESP monographs, textbooks and dictionaries were created in many areas. However, it is still an urgent issue to develop an English language teaching, assessment system and teaching resources suitable for students, their needs, requirements and level within a certain educational direction.

A general view on the theory of ESP

In the 21st century, the process of globalization and integration has affected all aspects and created a need for career-oriented communication in people. The role of English as a lingua franca in international trade created the goal of directing it to another area of life, thus the ESP educational direction appeared. ESP has developed as a branch of the EFL teaching model since the early 1960s. ESP did not start with new theories or ideas within any field, it has reached its current form only because of the need of the times. The adage commonly used in the West, "Necessity is the mother of invention" is aptly suited to the historical development of ESP. ESP has also undergone

many changes due to various developments in education, business, computing, information technology, global economy, applied linguistics and ELT. Many scholars around the world have given different definitions of ESP education, among which Dudley-Evans, Whitchinson, Tony were the first, then Tom and Water Alan, Stevens contributed to its further development. . Thousands of studies and scientific monographs have been created on this field of education, which has been at the center of research of world scientists since its establishment until now.

Hutchinson and Waters describe ESP as an approach rather than a specific language teaching material or methodology. According to them, the main element of learning a foreign language is the concept of "purpose", that is, why the learner is learning this language. ESP is an approach to language teaching, the content and purpose of which is determined by the needs of the learners. (Whitchinson and Waters, 1987:19). Looking at the history of ESP, there is a lot of information about it. However, according to Hutchinson and Waters (1987), its emergence can be summarized under three main factors. The reasons common to all ESP theories are as follows:

- 1) ESP can be related to a specific field or activity;
- 2) He can use teaching methods and situations different from General English;
- 3) ESP courses can be organized for adult learners with a medium and high level of knowledge.

Building on Hutchinson and Waters, Anthony (1997) suggests that their definition is correct but has several flaws. According to him, many non-specialist ESP teachers use the ESP approach in their curriculum, but they are not sure where to end the ESP course and when to start General English. ESP refers to the learning and teaching of a language and its skills to a specific group of learners for a specific purpose.

Dey and Krzanovsky conclude that ESP is always field-oriented. It consists of knowledge and skills that students will need in their work activities or careers in the field. In addition to the same argument, Schmitt and Richards acknowledge that the content and purpose of ESP courses are goal-oriented. Language learners also belong to a specific field or academic field. ESP suggests that it is based on two important criteria:

- 1) Orientation to a specific goal;
- 2) Covering needs and requirements.

ESP is the process of teaching English for useful purposes, in which the intended purpose refers to the academic, scientific or professional needs of language learners. The concept of specialized language means a certain list of words and expressions selected from the whole language, which are used to meet the demand in a certain field or situation. In the teaching of ESP, the term "specialized" is interpreted as a goal, that is, the goal of learners in language learning is understood. ESP courses are rarely organized around the need to teach important concepts in science, and students who complete language courses are expected to be able to read, understand and communicate knowledge in their field. ESP is traditionally divided into two main branches: English for Academic Purposes (EAP) and English for Professional Purposes (EOP). Later, other types of ESP emerged (Carter, 1983): restricted English, English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAOP), and English for Themes (EST). It is on the basis of this distribution that many areas such as tourism, business management, economy and banking, law, medicine, technology, accounting and English appeared. For example, Brigitte Planken and Katerina Nickerson, while analyzing business English, emphasize that, unlike traditional English, such courses should be closely related to the activities of people engaged in real business. English for Academic Purposes

(EAP) refers to the teaching of English in schools, colleges and universities, which are educational institutions, in which English is learned as a means of communication for science in the formal education system. However, professional English requires communication in professional fields such as medicine, engineering, aviation, and business. According to Hemp-Lyons (2001), ESP teaching methodology is a part of Applied Linguistics, which has a unique assessment system, analyzes students' language learning needs, and consists of linguistic and discursive structures of academic texts.

Strivens (1977) argues that English for academic purposes is different from the nature of reading literature or English speakers learning English for communicative purposes. The language should match the needs and goals of the learners. Academic English occurs in different conditions and situations. Academic English is necessary for students studying in higher education. Such targeted English courses can be of short or long duration. A course can be organized through a formal curriculum, distance learning materials, or non-traditional methods such as computer-assisted language learning. A general English course may provide learners with social genres or conversational knowledge of the language, but an academic English course teaches formal academic genres, while a professional English course teaches work-related genres. In short, academic and professional English courses are precisely because they teach specific vocabulary and grammatical form language competencies that are selected based on the purpose of the learners at a particular time. In addition, they are also from the topics and issues arising from the communicative needs of the applicants.

ESP was originally created specifically for new migrants and refugees as part of a larger English language teaching program in English-speaking countries, while EAP was offered to non-English speaking students visiting for academic purposes. However, the current trend is to spread ESP to non-English-speaking countries, where English is taught either as a second language or as a foreign language. English teacher Jones describes it as follows: “ESP is mainly seen in English as a foreign language situations, where large numbers of students are studying Business or Academic English. the increase in demand has an effect”. (43 pages)

ESP education is significantly different from traditional English language teaching EFL or ESL in features such as form, purpose, content, tasks, learning environment, assessment system, teacher and learner interests and responsibilities. The most important difference is felt in the difference between learners and their approach to learning English. ESP students are usually adults with partial or sufficient knowledge of English who are learning the language for a specific purpose in order to communicate within their field and perform tasks related to their profession. ESP can cover a variety of subjects, from Computing or Computer Technology to Tourism and Business Administration. Of course, in this case, English is not taught as a subject that is free from the wishes of students, but integrated in that subject. ESL and ESP differ not only in the nature of the learners, but also in the purpose of instruction. In fact, ESL emphasizes all language competencies: listening, reading, speaking, and writing. However, the analysis of students' needs will determine which language competence is emphasized in ESP, and the curriculum will be drawn up accordingly. The ESP program mainly focuses on the development of reading and speaking skills. For a long time, the importance of learning English for a specific purpose has been proven, and various studies and studies have been conducted on the organization of qualified EFL and ESP courses. The purpose of ESP courses has always been to develop students' language competence and lifelong learning. After all, as English becomes a lingua franca as a professional language

internationally, students aim to achieve their main academic goals by learning English, either as a second language or as a foreign language (Heydar & Delvand, 2015). Research shows that the ESP concentration is a course tailored to the specific needs of students in each major, with students aiming to study their subject in an international language. In fact, the term ESP and its tasks tend to consider some considerations such as the learning environment or place of learning, as well as the differences between students and teachers (Howatt, 1984). Attention is also paid to the nature of the language being taught. A long-standing debate in ESP and EFL education is that EFL teachers do not have sufficient subject knowledge. Dudley-Ewens and John (1998) emphasize that the role of the ESP teacher is important, that the teacher has the task not only to teach, but also to organize a good course and develop relevant materials. Teaching English to non-philology students requires 3 main activities and tasks: 1) organizational preparation stage (understanding the goals of the didactic process), being able to choose methodical support, dividing students into different groups, etc.; 2) didactic process related to the understanding of language goals; 3) the last stage - conclusion and adaptation to the educational process.

Requirements in the National Education Standards for non-philology B2 level students

The introduction of ESP technology into the educational field of Uzbekistan in 2016 in cooperation with the British Embassy and the scientific and practical innovation center of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan EnSPIRe-U (English for Specific Purposes Integrated Reform in Uzbekistan) as a result of the project, we mentioned above. The main goal of the program was to develop a curriculum, manual and assessment system for existing non-philological higher education institutions in the country. In ESP education, it was decided that the evaluation criteria, the teaching system will be based on the requirements of the international CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference) and Davtal educational standard. According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers on "Requirements for knowledge of foreign languages intended for all stages of education", students of non-philology majors in all higher education institutions in Uzbekistan must reach B2 level in the CEFR assessment system during the 7 semesters of education. they must acquire a suitable foreign language". Of course, taking into account the fact that a large number of students cannot achieve this in the educational environment of Uzbekistan, it was aimed to implement this project step by step.

Sociolinguistic competence makes it possible to choose the necessary linguistic form and expression method based on a speech situation, communicative goal and desire of the speaker. Sociolinguistic competence includes socio-cultural competence and shows the ability to present national characteristics of authentic speech: knowledge of customs, values, rituals and other national-cultural characteristics of the country where one lives and compares it with the country where the language is studied. holds.

Pragmatic competence refers to the ability to get out of difficult situations by repeatedly asking, apologizing, etc. In this standard, discourse competence was included in pragmatic competence. This competence involves expressing thoughts in oral or written speech using appropriate language tools. Discourse competence refers to the ability to understand and interpret linguistic signals to ensure consistency in oral or written speech.

The content of education consists of topics included in the curricula of general secondary, secondary special, vocational and higher education in subjects. Educational material provides

coherence, continuity and periodicity in all types of education. Based on the content of this standard, it is used as a minimum in the development of educational programs and textbooks at each level of education. The requirements for the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by graduates in foreign languages are developed in accordance with the educational content, general secondary education, secondary special, vocational and higher education. It is organized according to the text, the descriptors of speech skills and competences are described in the "can do" content and supplemented with grammar, lexis, phonetics and orthography where necessary. In order to adapt to international standards, the descriptors of speech skills and competences were interrelated to the pan-European system of knowledge of foreign languages, and they were presented in a simple and understandable form. Based on the requirements for the levels of knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by graduates, it can be described as follows:

— to be taken into account by the compilers in the development of curricula and textbooks at all stages of education to ensure full mastery of each level,

— In the Republic of Uzbekistan, all stages of education should be included in the development of evaluation criteria for the state certification of graduates.

In foreign language preparatory education for the B2 level: topics related to the Internet and information technologies, socio-cultural topics, comparison and comparison of the cultures of Uzbekistan and the countries where the language is studied; topics related to the field of specialization (history of the field of specialization, directions of the field), social topics (social relations with the environment) constitute such topics. Students' speech competence is developed through listening comprehension, speaking, reading, and language competence is formed through writing, lexical and grammatical competencies. In the listening comprehension competence, the learner can understand and observe a large-scale speech or a series of complex ideas, listen and understand the essence of lectures, speeches, statements, detailed instructions, scientific and specialized presentations, inquiries and opinions, e.g. can understand the content of texts and messages, complex authentic speech in familiar and unfamiliar contexts. Can understand the conversation or debate of native speakers of the target language, radio, internet and television programs, most of the interviews.

In conversational competence, he can verbally perform such tasks as being able to negotiate with his partners, be able to make a request on a certain issue, be able to communicate with speakers of the language being studied, and be able to manage if necessary. Can participate in live discussions and debates without prior preparation, can participate in interviews related to his field, can express his thoughts and opinions clearly in a formal discussion, can clarify, modify and correct his thoughts in discussions can use appropriate levels of formality and politeness when negotiating a deal or finding a solution to a problem, can ask and answer questions appropriately in a formal setting. If all this is manifested in interpersonal communication, the student will be able to perform a number of tasks on his own. Ability to give a good presentation on a specific topic, to be able to describe a number of things related to one's field clearly and in detail, to be able to give an oral presentation on a specific topic, an article, lecture or discussion to be able to make clear generalized conclusions, to develop a view or opinion on a familiar topic, to give evidence, examples, etc

In accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 124 of May 8, 2013, the state educational standard for teaching foreign languages in the continuing education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan was developed, which includes the

purpose and tasks, the content of teaching and learning a foreign language, the requirements for mandatory training levels of graduates of educational institutions at all stages of education were determined. Based on the state education standards, learning a foreign language is carried out at the following stages and at the levels set according to the pan-European international standard level:

1) Graduates of the 4th grade of general secondary education, A1, that is, the initial level of learning a foreign language; 9th grade graduates A2-basic level of foreign language learning; 9th grade graduates of specialized schools where foreign languages are taught in depth are required to acquire A2+ enhanced basic level of foreign language learning;

2) Graduates of academic lyceums of secondary special and professional education not specializing in foreign languages, graduates of vocational colleges and graduates of academic lyceums specializing in foreign languages (second foreign language) B1- independent initial level of foreign language learning; Graduates of academic lyceums specializing in foreign languages are required to reach the enhanced independent initial level of foreign language learning B1+;

3) Bachelor's degree graduates of higher education institutions with non-foreign language specialization, master's degree graduates of higher education institutions with non-foreign language specialization, and bachelor's degree graduates of higher education institutions with foreign language specialization (second foreign language) B2-level of independent communication of learning a foreign language; It has been shown that graduates of bachelor's degrees of higher education institutions specializing in foreign languages, and graduates of master's degrees of higher education institutions specializing in foreign languages have the C1 level of free communication in foreign language learning.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language at all stages of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the formation of communicative competence in a foreign language so that students can work in everyday, scientific and professional fields in a multicultural world:

1. Communicative competence
2. Linguistic competence
3. Sociolinguistic competence
4. Pragmatic competence

The content of education consists of topics included in the curricula of general secondary, secondary special, vocational and higher education in subjects. Educational material provides coherence, continuity and periodicity in all types of education. Based on the content of this standard, it is used as a minimum in the development of educational programs and textbooks at each level of education. The requirements for the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by graduates in foreign languages are developed in accordance with the educational content, general secondary education, secondary special, vocational and higher education. It is organized according to the text, the descriptors of speech skills and competences are described in the "can do" content and supplemented with grammar, lexis, phonetics and orthography where necessary. In order to adapt to international standards, the descriptors of speech skills and competences were interrelated to the pan-European system of knowledge of foreign languages, and they were presented in a simple and understandable form. Based on the requirements for the levels of knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by graduates, it can be described as follows:

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Conclusion

Although the topic of ESP has been extensively researched based on various approaches, there are still a number of scientific and professional areas that have not been studied. Monographs, dictionaries and textbooks on English language teaching for mathematics students were created in countries such as Moscow and Poland, which served as programming in this research process. The State Education Standards include the development of four main components of language: speaking, reading, writing, and listening, and various tasks for them at almost all language levels.

REFERENCES

1. Dudley-Evans, T. & St. John, M.J. www.camlang.com/art001.cfm -1998
2. Hutchinson, T., & Waters, A. 1987. English for Specific Purposes: A learning-centered approach. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Developments in English for Specific Purposes: A multi-disciplinary approach, Cambridge University Press.
3. Robinson, P. 1991 ESP Today: a Practitioner’s Guide. Hemel Hempstead: Prentice Hall International.
4. Strevens, P. 1988 ESP after twenty years: A re-appraisal. In M. Tickoo (Ed.), ESP: State of the Art (pp. 1-13). Singapore: SEAMEO Regional Centre.
5. Widdowson, H.G. 1983. Learning Purpose and Language Use. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
6. 2021-yil 19-maydagi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PQ- 5117-son “O‘zbekiston Respublikasida xorijiy tillarni o‘rganishni ommalashtirish faoliyatini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi qarori <https://lex.uz/docs/-5426736>
7. Linguodidactics and Methods English for Special Purposes (ESP) Toshmatov O.Sh. O‘zbekistonda xorijiy tillar, 2022, № 5 (46), 118-130
8. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining “Ta’lim muassasalarida chet tillar o‘qitishning sifatini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risidagi” 610-son qarori. <https://lex.uz/docs/3304915>
9. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 124 son qarori bilan tasdiqlangan —Uzluksiz ta’lim tizimining chet tillar bo‘yicha davlat ta’lim standarti. 2013 yil 8 may